

Software Engineering Practices in Brazilian Startups: A Survey of Practitioner Perspectives Protocol

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DOCUMENT HISTORY

This document is thought to be a live document. Once there is an update in the research, a new consideration, insight, improvement, this document must be updated with the new considerations.

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PLANNING

1. Research Objectives

The purpose of this work is to obtain more evidence regarding the use of software engineering practices (processes, methodologies, and tools) in software startups context from software development practitioners' point of view.

1.1 Research Question (RQ)

RQ1: What does software engineering practices startup use?

We aims acquire evidence of what software engineering practices software startups have been using.

RQ2: What tools software startups use to support software engineering practices?

The objective of this question is to investigate what tools have supported software engineering practices in startups.

RQ3: Are there any differences in the choice depending on the stage of the life cycle where it is?

We formulated this research question to investigate whether the software engineering practices adopted by startups change depending on their stage in the startup life-cycle.

2. Study Plan

This survey study planning consists of related works studies, such as the ones investigating the use of software engineering practices in software startups, the execution schedule, and a survey logbook.

2.1 Survey Guidelines

This are the list of works that oriented the Survey:

- Pfleeger et al. [1] focus on contextualizing what a survey is, what activities are involved in building one, and presenting three examples;
- Kitchenham et al. [2] addresses the process to design a survey;
- Kitchenham et al. [3] provide steps to construct the survey instrument;
- Kitchenham et al. [4] discuss how to avoid biased questions in survey instruments, motivate people to complete instruments and evaluate instruments;
- Kitchenham et al. [5] describe how to obtain a valid survey sample from the target population;
- Kitchenham et al. [6] discuss how to analyze survey data;
- Wohlin et al. [7] presents very briefly this empirical study;
- Linåker et al. [8] present guidelines that are adapted to software engineering research;

- Molléri et al. [9] systematically aggregate knowledge from 12 methodological studies supporting survey-based research in software engineering proposing a checklist that guides ongoing research and auditing survey reports.

2.2 Software Engineering Practices Investigations

Software Engineering Practices in Software Startups

- Paternoster et al. [10] conducted a systematic mapping study that investigates primary studies that report software development work practices in startups.
- Giardino et al. [11] characterize their context and identify common software development startup practices;
- Klotins et al. [12] identifies and categorizes software engineering knowledge areas utilized in startups to map out the state-of-art, identifying gaps for further research;
- Giardino et al. [13] performed this state-of-practice investigation using a grounded theory approach and packaged the results in the Greenfield Startup Model (GSM), which explains the priority of startups;
- Berg et al. [14] conducted a systematic mapping study that discovered that most research has been conducted within the SWEBOK knowledge areas software engineering process, management, construction, design, and requirements, with the shift of focus towards process and management areas. They provide an alternative classification for future startup research;
- Klotins et al. [15] investigate how software engineering is done in start-up companies, its influences and dependencies, with the focus to point towards gaps for further research. It was made by performing a multi-vocal exploratory study of 88 start-up experience reports.
- Klotins et al. [16] collect data related to engineering goals, challenges, and practices in start-up companies using a use a case survey method, and create the progression model guiding software engineering efforts in start-ups;
- Leal et al. [17] investigated start-up behaviors regarding which software development tools and practices they use;

2.3 Related Work

Survey in Software Engineering Practices in Software Startups

- Pantiuchina et al [???] targets at a better understanding of the use of agile practices in software startups, with a particular focus on lean startups through a large survey of 1526 software startups. They examined the use of five agile practices, including quality related (regular refactoring and test first), speed related (frequent release and agile planning) and communication practice (daily standup meeting).

2.4 Report Related Study

Evidence Briefing (EBs)

- Cartaxo et al. [18] selected a set of systematic reviews identified by a tertiary study and extracted their findings to generate one-page Evidence Briefings to serve as mediums;
- da Silva et al. [19] conducted a survey with practitioners from Brazilian Software Organizations (BSOs) investigate the participants' knowledge level on Technical Debt (TD)

and Technical Debt Management (TDM), including technologies adopted by practitioners from the industry. The results of this study were reported through Evidence Briefings (EB).

3. Target Population and Sampling

The Brazilian Startup Association created StartupBase, which is the official database of the Brazilian startup ecosystem. This base is available for internet access through the site <https://startupbase.com.br>.

Figure 1: Brazilian Startups

According to statistics for the year 2019, currently, the Brazilian scenario has more than 12 thousand startups divided into 77 ecosystems spread throughout the national territory, as shown in Figure 1.

To achieve the research objectives, software developers from software startups were selected as the target audience, while the population selected was Brazilians software startups. The survey should include questions to reveal the participants' job, their experience in software development and information on the organizations they work, such as size (ecosystem location) and project domain to characterize the survey participants.

For this survey, the unit of observation is the software development practitioner, while the unit of analysis is the startup's software development projects. Finally, the search unit is software startups. The sampling design adopted is accidental, a non-probabilistic type of sampling. For example, we cannot observe randomness on the selected units from the population. The only criterion adopted to select the units is convenience. An invitation to answer the survey was sent to a series of software startups in the country.

In order to achieve our goal, we defined the following criteria to include the participants in this survey study:

- work at a software startup;
- the software startup is located in a Brazilian startup ecosystem;

- perform the activity of software developers.

4. Instrument Design

The survey instrument was designed according to the guidelines presented in Linaker et al. [8]. A web-based questionnaire was chosen to reaching practitioners from other startup ecosystems besides the one situated in Salvador, where this research takes place. Also, due to Brazil's geographical constraints, this survey needs to be web-based. The questionnaire is composed mostly of closed questions with a small number of open questions to get further information from the participant.

Table 2: Questionnaire Section

Sections	Topic	Description
A	Research participation consent	To obtain voluntary agreement to participate in the survey research.
B	Participant's characterization	To obtain personal information regarding the participant, such as age, degrees, development experience, and position held.
C	Companies' characterization	To gather information about the companies where participant works: size in terms of the number of employees; size in terms of the number of developers in a project; foundation year; the number of customers; the number of products.
D	Product's Characterization	To obtain information about the startup's main product
1	Software requirements	To obtain information about the startup's software requirements engineering
2	Software design	To obtain information about the startup's software design
3	Software construction	To obtain information about the startup's software construction
4	Software testing	To obtain information about the startup's software testing
5	Software maintenance	To obtain information about the startup's software maintenance
6	Software configuration management	To obtain information about the startup's software configuration management
7	Software engineering management	To obtain information about the startup's software engineering management
8	Software engineering process	To obtain information about the startup's software engineering process

The Computing foundations and Mathematical foundations area is not part of the scope of this study.

4.1 Consent Research Form

This work aims to observe how Software Engineering practices have been adopted in the scenario of Brazilian software startups.

Your participation in this study is voluntary, and all data will be anonymized. The higher the participation, the more significant the results and contributions of this work will be to the Software Engineering Community.

The questionnaire consists of two stages: The first consists of characterizing the participant, details about the startup, and the development of the startup's product (s). The estimated average completion time is 10

minutes; The second stage includes questions related to the Software Engineering practices adopted by startups. The estimated average completion time is 15 minutes.

This study is part of the Doctorate research in Software Engineering by Renata Souza, student of the Postgraduate Program in Computer Science at the Federal University of Bahia (PGCOMP / UFBA), under the guidance of Prof. Ivan Machado.

This study adopts the ethical and scientific principles that guide scientific research in Experimental Software Engineering. In this way, personal and sensitive data are not requested. All results will be presented in an aggregated form, without the possibility of identifying the respondent.

If you have any questions or suggestions, please contact renatasouza@dcc.ufba.br.

4.2 Survey Instrument

The survey instrument was created using the tool: Survey Monkey (<https://www.surveymonkey.com/>).

4.2 Survey Closure

Agradecemos sua colaboração. Qualquer dúvidas ou sugestões, por favor entre em contato através do e-mail renatamss@ufba.br.

5. Instrument Validation

According to Linaker et al. (2015), a pilot trial is conducted using the same artifacts and procedures designed for the survey, including both the survey questionnaire and the execution method. This pilot is conducted with a small number of participants from the target population and survey experts to gather feedback.

The first researcher constructed the survey instrument. The instrument was validated in two stages: by the second researcher and by specialists. The survey instrument went through two rounds of analysis and adjustment involving the first and the second researcher. In the second phase, the survey instrument was released to seven specialists, two specialists in survey studies, two researchers and software developers, and two researchers specialized in software startups.

EXECUTION

6. Participant Recruitment

The invitation to the survey was sent by email, Facebook, Twitter and LinkedIn. The invitation text contains the main instructions and the questionnaire link. They were asked to answer the questionnaire and return their feedback regarding, but not restricted to: total response time; question chaining, i.e., whether the questions have a logical connection between them; a proper understanding of questions and answer options; answers completeness; the presence of ambiguity on questions and answers; clarity of the instructions; and, data collection and its analysis.

ANALYSIS AND REPORT

7. Data Analysis

In this section, we report the results of the analyzes of our research study. This research has an exploratory characteristic. To achieve the defined objectives, we adopted the following assumptions about the instrument:

1. For closed questions that had the objective of discovering the developer's perception regarding the formality of the practices applied to each area of Software Engineering, the participant could classify it as "formal", "informal", or "not applicable";
2. For closed questions with multiple responses, the sum of percentages should be 100%;
3. For closed questions that could combine multiple responses, the sum of percentages could be higher than 100%.

The survey results can be found in the following link:

<https://pt.surveymonkey.com/results/SM-9M6FTWSG7/>

8. Reporting

The reported intended audience of this work is the researchers and practitioners that work in software startups. More specifically, we will report the survey process, including data analysis and results in interpretation: (1) to researchers, we pretend to publish the findings of this study in PROFES 2020 (<https://softeng.polito.it/profes2020/>); and, (2) to practitioners, we will report through Evidence Briefings (EBs) (Cartaxo et al. [18]).

The EBs are going to summarize the acquired knowledge and provide means to transfer it from academia to the software industry. They provide information in a one-page briefing, simplifying the knowledge transfer process and improving the likelihood of it being acquired and adopted by software practitioners.

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